

Supplementary information
for
**Multi-Omic Analysis of *Tyrophagus putrescentiae* Reveals Insights into the
Allergen Complexity of Storage Mites**

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1 **Supplementary Methods**

2 ***Genome and transcriptome data***

3 The *T. putrescentiae* mites were cultured in Shenzhen University (Shenzhen, China) (1). The
4 genome and transcriptome data of *T. putrescentiae* have been reported (1) and deposited
5 under in the NCBI database under BioProject accession PRJNA706095. The genome exhibits
6 high quality with a completeness of over 90% and a good continuity indicated by a 2.9-Mbp
7 scaffold N50. The GenBank assembly accession of is GCA_021730765.1 and the SRA
8 accession of transcriptome data is SRR13837414 that contains three sets of original reads
9 (TP1, TP3 and TyrP2). We utilized two transcriptome data, namely TP1 and TP3, in our
10 study. These data were generated from RNA samples. The reason for excluding the additional
11 data (TyrP2) was that it was derived from a cDNA sample.

12

13 ***In silico identification of allergens***

14 The protein sequences of allergens in astigmatic mites were downloaded from the WHO/IUIS
15 allergen nomenclature database (2) (dated March 2022) as references. The reference allergens
16 were searched in the annotated protein sequences of *T. putrescentiae* genome (1) (GenBank
17 assembly accession: GCA_021730765.1) using BLASTP v2.9.0 (3) with the options ‘-evalue
18 1e-6 -max_hsps 1 -max_target_seqs 1 -outfmt 6’. The top matched proteins were candidate
19 allergens. Then, the transcriptome data were mapped to the genome using Hisat2 (4) and the
20 format conversion was performed by SAMtools (5). The sorted and indexed bam file was
21 visualized in the Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV) (6) and used for the manual curation of
22 the candidate allergens. The final *in silico* identified allergens were listed in Table S1 and the
23 sequences have been deposited in NCBI GenBank under accessions OP558975-OP559059.

24

1 ***Quantification of gene expression level***

2 To quantify the gene expression level of allergens, all the coding sequences (CDS) were
3 collected and indexed using Salmon v0.12.0 (7) with the options ‘-i index --type quasi -k 31’.
4 Then the TP1 and TP3 transcriptome reads (NCBI SRA accession: SRR13837414) were
5 mapped to the indexed CDS of all allergens using Salmon v0.12.0 (7) and the gene
6 expression levels were represented by the TPM (transcript per million). As for the gene
7 expression of Niemann-Pick proteins type C2 (NPC2) family and glutathione S-transferases
8 (GSTs), the CDS of target genes were used as indexes, respectively.

9

10 ***Cloning, expression, and ELISA of recombinant proteins***

11 Protein and CDS sequences of six *T. putrescentiae* proteins were obtained after manual
12 curation in the genome. The codon-optimized CDS sequences were synthesized and
13 subcloned into plasmid vector (pET-28a+), and then expressed into recombinant proteins in
14 TOP10 *E. coli*. The codon-optimized CDS sequences were synthesized and subcloned into
15 plasmid vector, and then transformed in *E. coli* cells. The *E. coli* cells were induced by
16 isopropyl β -D-1-thiogalactopyranoside (final concentration: 1 mM) for protein expression
17 and incubated at 20 °C for 16 hours or 37 °C for 4 hours. Proteins were extracted after cell
18 ultrasonication, and 12% (w/v) SDS-PAGE analysis were performed to determine the protein
19 solubility. The recombinant proteins were finally purified to over 90% by Ni²⁺ affinity
20 chromatography using a fast protein liquid chromatography system. The five recombinant
21 proteins rTyr p 6.0101, 9.0101, 18.0101, 20.0101 and 26.0101 were initially insoluble, then
22 were denatured and purified from inclusion body pellets, and finally refolded in dialysis. The
23 recombinant protein of FK506-binding protein (TP_004518.01) was soluble and purified
24 from supernatant after centrifuge. We successfully obtained all the recombinant proteins with
25 a purity level exceeding 90%. The cloning and expression of the recombinant proteins were

1 performed by Sangon Biotech (Shanghai, China).
2
3 The allergenicity of the recombinant proteins was assessed by the enzyme-linked
4 immunosorbent assay (ELISA). For the experiments, serum samples were obtained from 18
5 patients who presented with positive SPT or ImmunoCAP results towards *T. putrescentiae*
6 (d72), and from 13 healthy individuals who served as negative controls (Table S2). In the
7 indirect sandwich ELISA, a 96-well microtiter plate was coated with 100 ul (2 ug/ml) of
8 recombinant proteins per well in sodium bicarbonate coating buffer (0.1 mol/L, pH 9.5). The
9 plate was washed by 0.05% Tween-20 in PBS washing buffer for 4 times and then was
10 blocked with 375 ul 3% skim milk in PBST buffer for 30 minutes at 37°C. Serum samples
11 were diluted 1:4 in PBST containing 1% BSA and 50 ul was added to each blocked well for 1
12 hr at room temperature. After washing, IgE antibodies were detected using biotinylated goat
13 anti-human IgE (Vector, Burlingame, CA, USA) and streptavidin peroxidase (Sigma-Aldrich,
14 St. Louis, MO, USA). The wells were then washed again with PBST buffer and incubated
15 with 100 ul 3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine (Kirkegaard and Perry Laboratories,
16 Gaithersburg, MD, USA) for 15 mins at room temperature. The reactions ceased with the
17 addition of 2M sulphuric acid (50 ul/well). The plates were then placed in the Benchmark
18 Plus Microplate Spectrophotometer (BioRad, Hercules, CA, USA) and absorbance at 450 nm
19 was recorded, where a high absorbance is indicative of a high concentration.

20

21 ***2D gel electrophoresis, immunoblotting and MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry***

22 Two-dimension (2D) gel electrophoresis was performed by Shenzhen University. Serum
23 samples were obtained at The First Affiliated Hospital of Guangzhou Medical University
24 from 25 patients (mean age, 19.9 years; range, 2–51 years, Table S3) who presented with
25 allergic rhinitis and/or asthma and were examined for dust mite allergies.

1

2 In brief, the final concentration of total protein extracted from *T. putrescentiae* was adjusted
3 to 1.5 ug/ul. 2D- polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (PAGE) was performed in duplicate
4 using 300 ug total protein per gel. The first gel was used for IgE-blot analysis to locate dust
5 mite antigens, while the second gel was stained with Coomassie blue (Sigma, St. Louis, MO,
6 USA) for cutting spots of allergen candidates. These putative allergen spots were then
7 processed to MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry analysis.

8

9 In 2D gel electrophoresis, the first-dimension separation step was to separate protein mixture
10 by the isoelectric point (pI). Isoelectric focusing (IEF) was performed by two immobilized
11 pH gradient (IPG) strips (pH 3.0–10.0 and pH 4.0–7.0). In each gel, 300 ug proteins were
12 used and make up to 125 ul using 8M Urea, 2% CHAPS, 65 mM DTT, 0.5% v/v IPG buffer
13 pH 3-10 and 0.001% bromophenol blue. The entire 7 cm precast gel tapes were soaked in 125
14 ul protein extracts for an hour and covered with mineral oil. The focus tray was put into the
15 IEF instrument for running (operating voltage followed by 50 V 12 hrs, 250 V 30 mins, 500
16 V 30 mins, 4 kV 3 hrs, 4 kV 20,000 Vh). After the isoelectric focusing, the strips were
17 washed with distilled water and then put into the equilibration buffer I (0.375 mol/L Tris-HCl,
18 6 mol/L urea, 20% glycerol, 2% SDS, 2% DTT) for 15 mins and rinsed with distilled water.
19 The strips were then shaken gently for 15 mins in equilibration buffer II (0.375 mol/L Tris-
20 HCl, 6 mol/L urea, 20% glycerol, 2% SDS, 2.5% iodoacetamide), and rinsed with distilled
21 water.

22

23 The second-dimension electrophoresis was used to separate proteins according to their
24 molecular mass in a 12% sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-
25 PAGE) gel. Prior to SDS-PAGE, an equilibration step was applied to the first gel. The

1 separated proteins on IEF gel were complexed with SDS, reduced with DTT, and then
2 alkylated with iodoacetamide. After that, the equilibrated strip was loaded horizontally into
3 an SDS-PAGE gel and was secured by overlaying with molten agarose solution. The gel was
4 loaded into the electrophoresis cell and run in 60 V for 20 mins and then 120 V voltage for 2
5 hrs. The separated proteins were then transferred from the gels onto PVDF membranes. The
6 PVDF membranes were blocked with 3% bovine serum albumin (BSA) at 4 °C overnight,
7 and incubated with pooled sera (dilution ratio, 1:10) from 25 patients, followed by applying
8 an anti-human biotin-conjugated secondary antibody. IgE-allergen bound spots were
9 conjugated with mouse anti-human IgE Horseradish Peroxidase Streptavidin (HRP) (1:2000)
10 and signals were developed with 3,3'-diaminobenzidine (DAB). Spots in another parallel
11 Coomassie blue stained gel were excised according to the corresponding position of the IgE-
12 bound spots. After trypsin digestion, the excised protein samples were analyzed by MALDI-
13 TOF mass spectrometry.

14

15 The peptide fingerprinting and bioinformatic identification of the IgE-bound proteins is
16 achieved using MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry. The Coomassie blue-stained protein spots
17 were destained with 50% methanol/10 mM ammonium bicarbonate (NH₄HCO₃) solution,
18 and then dehydrated repeatedly with acetonitrile (ACN). The gel spots were dried in a
19 vacuum centrifuge and rehydrated with freshly prepared trypsin enzyme in a buffer (20 ng/ul
20 trypsin in 10 mM Ammonium bicarbonate), followed by incubating on ice for 15 mins. The
21 gel spots were incubated overnight at 30 °C for digestion. Half volume of 80% acetonitrile/
22 2.5% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) was added to each tube, and each extract was sonicated for
23 10 minutes.

24

25 Digested samples (0.5 ul each) were spotted onto stainless steel MALDI-plates and left to dry

1 at room temperature, followed by 0.5 ul matrix solution (5 mg/ml α -Cyano-4-
2 hydroxycinnamic acid in 50% CAN/0.5% TFA). The instrument and MALDI plate were
3 calibrated by a calibration mixture (desArgl-Bradykinin, Angiotensin I, Glul-Fibrinopeptide
4 B and Neurotensin). The target plate was inserted into ABI 4700 TOF-TOF Proteomics
5 Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Framingham, MA, USA) instrument. All the mass
6 spectrometry spectra were acquired using reflectron positive-ion mode over mass range m/z
7 700-4000 with acceleration at 20 kV in batch mode. Five to eight abundant peptide precursor
8 ions were chosen automatically for tandem MS/MS analysis with collision-induced
9 dissociation (CID) for each sample. Air was used as collision gas and the collision energy
10 was 1 kV.

11
12 The annotated protein sequences of *T. putrescentiae* were used as the database for peptide
13 search. The mass spectrometry data were searched by GPS Explorer using the search engine
14 MASCOT (Matrix Sciences, London, United Kingdom). For peptide fingerprinting, the
15 searches were performed with a peptide mass tolerance of 50 ppm. Significant hits were
16 determined by Mascot probability analysis and targets with at least two matches were
17 accepted. Combined (MS+MS/MS) analysis was performed for proteins that failed to be
18 identified by peptide fingerprinting. The search was performed with a peptide mass tolerance
19 of 50 ppm, MS/MSion mass tolerance of 0.1 Da, one missed cleavage, and oxidation of
20 methionine.

21 22 ***Comparative analyses of gene families***

23 All proteins of the six astigmatic mites were searched by BLASTP v2.9.0 (3) with reference
24 proteins at E-value cutoff of 1E-6. All the group 2, 22 and 35 allergens of astigmatic mite in
25 the WHO/IUIS allergen nomenclature database (2) (dated March 2022) were used for

1 searching NPC2 family genes, while all GSTs in Swiss-Prot database (8) (dated October
2 2021) were used for the GSTs of mites. After manual curation based on transcriptome data to
3 confirm intron-exon split sites and filtering out annotated proteins with shorter than 50%
4 average length of the gene family, all proteins of the six astigmatic mites identified in the
5 target gene families were aligned and drawn into a phylogenetic tree. Sequence alignment
6 was performed by CLUSTAL W (9) and MUSCLE (10) in MEGA v11.0.13 (11), and all
7 phylogenetic trees were constructed by MEGA v11.0.13 (11) with maximum likelihood (ML)
8 algorithm in the JTT (Jones-Taylor-Thornton) model, 80% site coverage and 100 bootstrap
9 replicates, and then edited by the online tool Interactive Tree of Life (iTOL) (12).

10

11 If two genes were located adjacently on genome and no other gene was located between
12 them, they were considered as tandemly arrayed genes. If two genes were separated by no
13 more than 10 genes, they were considered as proximally arrayed. Frequent tandemly arrayed
14 genes were identified in gene families and connected with curve lines in phylogenetic trees
15 edited by the online tool iTOL (12) with validated gene synteny information.

16

17 ***Ethical approval***

18 This study was approved by the institutional review board (IRB no. 4-2013-0397) of Institute
19 of Allergy, College of Medicine, Yonsei University for using the patient sera in ELISA
20 experiments and the hospital ethics committee of The First Affiliated Hospital of Guangzhou
21 Medical University (reference no. 2017018) for using the pooled patient sera in
22 immunoblotting (western blotting) following the 2D gel electrophoresis.

23

1 **Supplementary Notes**

2 *1. Genomic analysis of T. putrescentiae allergens*

3 *In silico* genomic analysis of *T. putrescentiae* predicted a wide range of allergen homologs,
4 including many tandemly duplicates (Figure S1). In our naming rules, we used the first and
5 last two digits after the decimal point to differentiate the different genes and isoforms,
6 respectively. For example, the two homologs of Tyr p 2, TP_003565.02 and TP_003567.01,
7 shared identical protein and coding sequences but were named Tyr p 2.0101 and Tyr p
8 2.0201, respectively (Table S1). Isoforms originating from the same gene locus were not
9 included, such as those caused by single-nucleotide polymorphisms or alternative splicing.

10

11 The heterogeneity of mite culture could cause artificial frameshifts in the genome annotation
12 (Figure S2) and all the allergen genes have been cautiously curated with high-coverage
13 transcriptome data. A wide range of gene expansion was observed in the allergen gene
14 families and only those top matched homologs (or isoallergens) were listed, such as five
15 homologs of the cysteine protease Tyr p 1 (Table S1). Most of the reported allergens of *T.*
16 *putrescentiae* could be found in the list, except genes like Tyr p 8 and 20 which lack highly
17 similar homologs (Figure S3). The discrepancy can be attributed to intragenic divergence of
18 *T. putrescentiae*, except that the best match of Tyr p 8 shared only 63.9% identity.

19

20 In the group 1 allergen, the best matched gene Tyr p 1.0101 (gene locus: TP_010062.02)
21 shared as high as 98.8% identity with the reported Tyr p 1 (Table S1). Three homologs (pTyr
22 p 1.0201, pTyr p 1.0301 and pTyr p 1.0401) were tandemly arrayed and located closely (less
23 than 5 kb in distance) on the same strand (Figure S1).

24

25 Group 3, 6 and 9 allergens are all serine proteases that have been reported to have massive
26 tandem gene duplication in astigmatic mites (1). The best matched Tyr p 3.0101 shared

1 93.6% identity with the reported Tyr p 3 (Table S1, Figure S3A). Of the seven homologs of
2 Tyr p 3, three genes (Tyr p 3.0101, pTyr p 3.0201 and pTyr p 3.0301) were tandemly arrayed
3 (Figure S1) and pTyr p 3.0201 was identified as a dimeric trypsin containing two duplicated
4 domains, while pTyr p 3.0401, pTyr p 3.0501 and pTyr p 3.0601 shared identical protein and
5 coding sequences. Consistent with a previous report, the global expression levels of serine
6 protease allergens were relatively higher than those of group 1 cysteine proteases (13).

7

8 Only one alpha-amylase gene of *T. putrescentiae* (1, 14), Tyr p 4.0101, was identified as
9 highly similar to the reported Tyr p 4 (99.0% identity, Table S1). Group 5 and 21 allergens are
10 the major allergens of *Blomia (B.) tropicalis* (15-17), but have not been reported in *T.*
11 *putrescentiae*. We identified three homologs of Tyr p 5 (including dimeric pTyr p 5.0301) and
12 one of Tyr p 21 (Table S1), all of which were tandemly arrayed (Figure S1).

13

14 Tyr p 7.0101 shared 99.1% identity with the reported Tyr p 7 (Table S1), while unexpectedly,
15 the best matched homolog of the group 8 allergen pTyr p 8.0101 shared only 63.9% identity
16 with the reported Tyr p 8 (GenBank accession: AGG10560, Figure S3B).

17

18 Two tandemly arrayed homologs of Tyr p 20, pTyr p 20.0101 and pTyr p 20.0201 (gene
19 locus: TP_001138.03 and TP_001138.02) shared 88.2% and 87.1% identities with the
20 reported Tyr p 20 (GenBank accession: QOI58528, Figure S3C), respectively. In addition, the
21 best matched genes of Tyr p 35 and 36 shared 85.1% and 91.6% identities with the reported
22 allergens, respectively (Figure S3D and E). Due to space limitations, we will not discuss
23 other allergen groups exhaustively.

24

1 2. *Immunoassay of recombinant proteins*

2 Five recombinant proteins for the newly *in-silico* predicted allergens were cloned and
3 expressed to evaluate their allergenicity. IgE reactivity was represented by absorbance value
4 at 450 nm assessed by the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) with the sera of 18
5 allergy patients that were positive to *T. putrescentiae* in skin prick test (Table S2). The five
6 recombinant proteins (Figure S4) showed various allergenicities with at least two patient sera
7 presented significantly higher IgE levels than those of 13 negative controls (Figure S5).

8

9 For the two serine protease allergens, the recombinant proteins rTyr p 6.0101 and rTyr p
10 9.0101 presented low allergenicities of 11.1% and 22.2%, respectively (Figure S5A and B).
11 Similarly, the chitinase rTyr p 18.0101 tested positive in only two samples (11.1%, Figure
12 S5C). For the arginine kinase and the myosin light-chain, rTyr p 20.0101 and rTyr p 26.0101
13 exhibited higher allergenicities, 44.4% and 50.0%, respectively (Figure S5D and E).
14 Although all the patients were diagnosed with *T. putrescentiae* sensitized by skin prick test
15 (Table S2), only 11/18 (61.1%) of the serum samples showed positive responses to the crude
16 protein extract (Figure S5F). However, all the absorbance values representing IgE antibody
17 levels were quite low (<0.1), which suggested that the five proteins were novel but minor
18 allergens of *T. putrescentiae*.

19

20 3. *Comparative analysis of GST family*

21 To better understand the allergen complexity of *T. putrescentiae*, comparative genomics was
22 performed for allergen gene families. Comparative genomic analysis has revealed the
23 divergent evolution of astigmatic mites (1). Our multi-omic identification of allergen
24 homologs in *T. putrescentiae* indicated the necessity of comparative analyses of the allergen
25 gene families.

1

2 In the Mu-class GST Mu, group 8 allergen can also cause cross-reactivity among astigmatic
3 mites (18). Similarly, the GSTs of six astigmatic mites were phylogenetically analyzed
4 (Figure S8A). Six clusters were divided, and all reported allergens were in Cluster GST Mu.
5 Unexpectedly, none of the GST genes were identical to the reported Tyr p 8 (GenBank
6 accession: AGG10560). Intriguingly, massive tandem gene duplications were observed
7 especially in the allergen cluster, Cluster GST Mu (Figure S8A). Unlike the ungrouped Tyr p
8 1 and 13 (Table 1), the proteomically identified GST (ungrouped Tyr p 8, gene locus:
9 TP_014174.01) was a lowly expressed homolog, which was unexpected (Figure S8B).

10

Table S1. Overview summary of all allergen genes predicted in *T. putrescentiae*

In our naming rules, we used the first and last two digits after the decimal point to differentiate the different genes and isoforms, respectively. To avoid confusion, we named the predicted allergen homologs with a prefix p that means putative.

Allergen ID	Isoallergen ID	Gene locus	GenBank accession	Biochemical function	No. of exons	No. of amino acids	TPM value (Avg±Stdev)	Homologue (Protein identity)
Tyr p 1	Tyr p 1.0101*	TP_010062.02	OP558975	Cysteine protease	5	336	25±13	ABM53753 Tyr p 1 (98.8%)
	pTyr p 1.0201#	TP_003057.02	OP558976	Cysteine protease	5	346	307±49	ABM53753 Tyr p 1 (46.0%)
	pTyr p 1.0301#	TP_003057.03	OP558977	Cysteine protease	5	343	105±17	ABM53753 Tyr p 1 (41.4%)
	pTyr p 1.0401#	TP_003059.01	OP558978	Cysteine protease	4	343	639±26	ABM53753 Tyr p 1 (39.1%)
	pTyr p 1.0501#	TP_011220.01	OP558979	Cysteine protease	5	341	486±52	ABM53753 Tyr p 1 (39.0%)
Tyr p 2	Tyr p 2.0101*	TP_003565.02	OP558980	NPC2 family	2	141	11776±2386	CAA73221 Tyr p 2 (99.3%)
	Tyr p 2.0201*	TP_003567.01	OP558981	NPC2 family	2	141	11776±2386	CAA73221 Tyr p 2 (99.3%)
	pTyr p 2.0301#	TP_019440.02	OP558982	NPC2 family	3	142	192±37	CAA73221 Tyr p 2 (70.4%)
	pTyr p 2.0401#	TP_019491.01	OP558983	NPC2 family	2	142	76±34	CAA73221 Tyr p 2 (69.7%)
	pTyr p 2.0501#	TP_003565.03	OP558984	NPC2 family	2	144	1061±40	CAA73221 Tyr p 2 (63.6%)
	pTyr p 2.0601#	TP_003565.04	OP558985	NPC2 family	2	142	6606±717	CAA73221 Tyr p 2 (63.6%)
Tyr p 3	Tyr p 3.0101*	TP_012006.03	OP558986	Trypsin	4	285	1374±691	ABZ81991 Tyr p 3 (93.6%)
	pTyr p 3.0201#	TP_012006.04	OP558987	Trypsin	6	535	59±17	ABZ81991 Tyr p 3 (69.8% / 60.7%)
	pTyr p 3.0301#	TP_012006.02	OP558988	Trypsin	4	288	4±3	ABZ81991 Tyr p 3 (66.8%)
	pTyr p 3.0401#	TP_014815.01	OP558989	Trypsin	3	262	40218±11917	ABZ81991 Tyr p 3 (51.5%)
	pTyr p 3.0501#	TP_014833.01	OP558990	Trypsin	3	262	40218±11917	ABZ81991 Tyr p 3 (51.5%)
	pTyr p 3.0601#	TP_022179.01	OP558991	Trypsin	3	262	40218±11917	ABZ81991 Tyr p 3 (51.5%)
Tyr p 4	Tyr p 4.0101*	TP_001226.01	OP558993	Alpha-amylase	5	518	1074±34	ABZ81991 Tyr p 4 (99.0%)
	pTyr p 5.0101#	TP_014187.01	OP558994	Unknown	4	135	3590±407	AAD10850 Blo t 5 (53.3%)
pTyr p 5	pTyr p 5.0201#	TP_014182.03	OP558995	Unknown	2	128	691±276	AAD10850 Blo t 5 (39.8%)
	pTyr p 5.0301#	TP_014182.02	OP558996	Unknown	2	236	11±3	AAD10850 Blo t 5 (36.3%)
pTyr p 6	pTyr p 6.0101#	TP_021257.01	OP558997	Chymotrypsin	4	275	23087±10331	AAF28423 Der f 6 (55.4%)
Tyr p 7	Tyr p 7.0101*	TP_021945.01	OP558998	Bactericidal/permeability-increasing protein	5	212	1119±193	ABM53750 Tyr p 7 (99.1%)
pTyr p 8	pTyr p 8.0101#	TP_016261.02	OP558999	Glutathione S-transferase	3	223	4990±109	AGG10560 Tyr p 8 (63.9%)
pTyr p 9	pTyr p 9.0101#	TP_010332.01	OP559000	Serine protease	3	270	43046±11849	AAP57077 Der p 9 (55.1%)
	pTyr p 9.0201#	TP_015698.02	OP559001	Serine protease	2	299	300±53	AAP57077 Der p 9 (48.7%)
Tyr p 10	Tyr p 10.0101*	TP_005966.01	OP559002	Tropomyosin	8	284	36103±2786	AAT40866 Tyr p 10 (98.6%)
	pTyr p 10.0201#	TP_002355.01	OP559003	Tropomyosin	7	253	3126±464	AAT40866 Tyr p 10 (56.8%)
Tyr p 11	Tyr p 11.0101*	TP_012922.01	OP559004	Paramyosin	12	875	6138±548	UXW65969 Tyr p 11 (97.6%)
pTyr p 12	pTyr p 12.0101#	TP_009564.03	OP559005	Chitin-binding domain containing protein	2	167	1424±63	AAA78904 Blo t 12 (49.2%)
Tyr p 13	Tyr p 13.0101*	TP_016572.02	OP559006	Fatty acid-binding protein	2	131	34448±939	AAU11502 Tyr p 13 (100%)
	pTyr p 13.0201#	TP_016572.03	OP559007	Fatty acid-binding protein	3	130	174146±22801	AAU11502 Tyr p 13 (66.9%)
	pTyr p 13.0301#	TP_005581.01	OP559008	Fatty acid-binding protein	3	130	48327±13467	AAU11502 Tyr p 13 (60.8%)
	pTyr p 13.0401#	TP_013995.02	OP559009	Fatty acid-binding protein	2	132	6136±745	AAU11502 Tyr p 13 (52.8%)
	pTyr p 13.0501#	TP_021718.01	OP559010	Fatty acid-binding protein	2	132	4833±714	AAU11502 Tyr p 13 (50.0%)
pTyr p 14	pTyr p 14.0101#	TP_017885.01	OP559011	Apolipoprotein	6	1681	8650±255	AAM21322 Der p 14 (45.5%)
pTyr p 15	pTyr p 15.0101#	TP_009564.02	OP559012	Chitinase	4	560	1820±190	AAY84565 Der p 15 (72.5%)
	pTyr p 15.0201#	TP_009563.02	OP559013	Chitinase	4	554	2380±381	AAY84565 Der p 15 (72.0%)
pTyr p 16	pTyr p 16.0101#	TP_020865.01	OP559014	Gelsolin/villin	8	497	963±33	AAM64112 Der f 16 (54.5%)
pTyr p 18	pTyr p 18.0101#	TP_001639.01	OP559015	Chitinase	4	464	4431±171	AAM19082 Der f 18 (59.1%)
	pTyr p 18.0201#	TP_021623.01	OP559016	Chitinase	4	464	4431±171	AAM19082 Der f 18 (59.1%)
	pTyr p 18.0301#	TP_022773.02	OP559017	Chitinase	4	466	1282±26	AAM19082 Der f 18 (55.0%)

(to be continued)

Allergen ID	Isoallergen ID	Gene locus	GenBank accession	Biochemical function	No. of exons	No. of amino acids	TPM value (Avg±Stdev)	Homologue (Protein identity)
Tyr p 20	pTyr p 20.0101 [#]	TP_001138.03	OP559018	Arginine kinase	4	356	9868±886	QOI58528 Tyr p 20 (88.2%)
	pTyr p 20.0201 [#]	TP_001138.02	OP559019	Arginine kinase	5	392	17212±1384	QOI58528 Tyr p 20 (87.1%)
pTyr p 21	pTyr p 21.0101 [#]	TP_014185.01	OP559020	Unknown	4	138	3472±202	AAD10850 Blo t 21 (61.3%)
pTyr p 23	pTyr p 23.0101 [#]	TP_019120.02	OP559021	Peritrophin-like protein	1	229	438±25	ACB46292 Der p 23 (45.1%)
pTyr p 24	pTyr p 24.0101 [#]	TP_009264.02	OP559022	UQCRB protein	4	118	47455±5790	AGI78542 Der f 24 (63.6%)
pTyr p 25	pTyr p 25.0101 [#]	TP_010799.02	OP559023	Triphosphate isomerase	4	247	15900±1082	AGC56216 Der f 25 (79.4%)
pTyr p 26	pTyr p 26.0101 [#]	TP_009336.02	OP559024	Myosin light-chain	5	158	49121±1725	QAT18638 Der p 26 (87.8%)
	pTyr p 28.0101 [#]	TP_011342.02	OP559025	Heat shock protein 70	3	659	14066±3095	AOD75395 Tyr p 28 (90.9%)
Tyr p 28	pTyr p 28.0201 [#]	TP_011350.01	OP559026	Heat shock protein 70	3	655	5912±792	AOD75395 Tyr p 28 (90.6%)
	pTyr p 28.0301 [#]	TP_022700.02	OP559027	Heat shock protein 70	5	644	1±2	AOD75395 Tyr p 28 (83.2%)
	pTyr p 28.0401 [#]	TP_015983.01	OP559028	Heat shock protein 70	1	645	1817±36	AOD75395 Tyr p 28 (80.8%)
	pTyr p 28.0501 [#]	TP_000248.01	OP559029	Heat shock protein 70	2	639	1322±107	AOD75395 Tyr p 28 (78.7%)
pTyr p 29	pTyr p 29.0101 [#]	TP_004508.01	OP559030	Cyclophilin	3	331	315±121	QAT18640 Der p 29 (69.3%)
pTyr p 30	pTyr p 30.0101 [#]	TP_016485.02	OP559031	Ferritin	1	107	1015±192	QAT18641 Der p 30 (83.5%)
	pTyr p 30.0201 [#]	TP_021342.02	OP559032	Ferritin	3	175	51401±3389	QAT18641 Der p 30 (83.5%)
	pTyr p 30.0301 [#]	TP_021345.02	OP559033	Ferritin	2	347	1090±179	QAT18641 Der p 30 (83.5%)
	pTyr p 30.0401 [#]	TP_021341.01	OP559034	Ferritin	2	172	13121±440	QAT18641 Der p 30 (81.6%)
Tyr p 31	Tyr p 31.0101 [*]	TP_010684.02	OP559035	Cofilin	4	148	49319±7596	UXW65975 Tyr p 31 (100%)
Tyr p 32	Tyr p 32.0101 [*]	TP_016449.02	OP559036	Inorganic pyrophosphatase	2	294	5123±879	UXW65973 Tyr p 32 (100%)
pTyr p 33	pTyr p 33.0101 [#]	TP_014283.02	OP559037	Alpha-tubulin	6	451	4882±1325	AIO08861 Der f 33 (83.7%)
	pTyr p 33.0201 [#]	TP_000522.01	OP559038	Alpha-tubulin	6	450	22499±4863	AIO08861 Der f 33 (82.7%)
	pTyr p 33.0301 [#]	TP_000118.02	OP559039	Alpha-tubulin	8	347	930±110	AIO08861 Der f 33 (80.2%)
	pTyr p 33.0401 [#]	TP_019973.02	OP559040	Alpha-tubulin	6	446	4868±1279	AIO08861 Der f 33 (79.6%)
	pTyr p 33.0501 [#]	TP_008758.02	OP559041	Alpha-tubulin	7	450	5301±1043	AIO08861 Der f 33 (78.5%)
Tyr p 34	Tyr p 34.0101 [*]	TP_005620.02	OP559053	Troponin C	5	153	46444±821	ACL36923 Tyr p 34 (100%)
Tyr p 35	pTyr p 35.0101 [#]	TP_014714.03	OP559055	Aldehyde dehydrogenase	5	487	10169±1661	AOD75396 Tyr p 35 (85.1%)
	pTyr p 35.0201 [#]	TP_014714.02	OP559056	Aldehyde dehydrogenase	5	481	18053±266	AOD75396 Tyr p 35 (74.7%)
	pTyr p 35.0301 [#]	TP_004844.03	OP559057	Aldehyde dehydrogenase	5	483	138±27	AOD75396 Tyr p 35 (67.8%)
	pTyr p 35.0401 [#]	TP_004844.02	OP559058	Aldehyde dehydrogenase	5	483	2220±78	AOD75396 Tyr p 35 (67.6%)
Tyr p 36	pTyr p 36.0101 [#]	TP_007980.01	OP559059	Profilin	3	131	61340±10960	AOD75399 Tyr p 36 (91.6%)
pTyr p 37	pTyr p 37.0101 [#]	TP_000195.01	OP559048	Chitin binding protein	3	248	1716±221	QBF67839 Der f 37 (44.9%)
	pTyr p 37.0201 [#]	TP_019138.01	OP559049	Chitin binding protein	2	218	720±28	QBF67839 Der f 37 (44.5%)
pTyr p 38	pTyr p 38.0101 [#]	TP_012405.02	OP559050	Bacteriolytic enzyme	4	153	819±340	QHQ72282 Der f 38 (58.8%)
	pTyr p 38.0201 [#]	TP_012405.03	OP559051	Bacteriolytic enzyme	3	153	22±5	QHQ72282 Der f 38 (54.2%)
	pTyr p 38.0301 [#]	TP_019308.02	OP559052	Bacteriolytic enzyme	2	144	47±10	QHQ72282 Der f 38 (50.7%)
pTyr p 40	pTyr p 40.0101 [#]	TP_011775.02	OP559054	Thioredoxin-like protein	3	165	28168±2971	UJQ69787 Der f 40 (68.6%)
pTyr p 41	pTyr p 41.0101 [#]	TP_020961.02	OP559042	Rid-like protein	1	137	4617±121	BAV90601 Der f 34* (59.1%)
	pTyr p 41.0201 [#]	TP_012005.01	OP559043	Rid-like protein	1	138	777±70	BAV90601 Der f 34* (37.1%)
pTyr p 42	pTyr p 42.0101 [#]	TP_004901.01	OP559046	Unknown	2	223	5679±33	ATI08932 Der f 36* (52.4%)
	pTyr p 42.0201 [#]	TP_006471.02	OP559044	Unknown	3	222	1122±85	ATI08932 Der f 36* (48.9%)
	pTyr p 42.0301 [#]	TP_020584.01	OP559045	Unknown	3	235	9155±619	ATI08932 Der f 36* (47.1%)
	pTyr p 42.0401 [#]	TP_010549.02	OP559047	Unknown	3	236	97±20	ATI08932 Der f 36* (41.7%)

* These genes were suggested as identical allergen genes by the high identity (higher than 92%) to those reported in the WHO/IUIS Allergen Nomenclature database.

These genes shared high similarities with the allergens reported in the WHO/IUIS Allergen Nomenclature database and were predicted to be putative allergen genes (labelled with a prefix p).

& Considering Tyr p 34 and 36 have been reported, the homologs of Der f 34 and 36 were named Tyr p 41 and 42, respectively.

Table S2. Metadata of the patient sera for ELISA experiment

Serum samples were collected by Institute of Allergy, Department of Internal Medicine, College of Medicine, Yonsei University (Seoul, Korea). All the patient sera were tested to be positive in SPT or ImmunoCAP towards *T. putrescentiae* (ImmunoCAP allergen d72). In the SPT column, H means histamine. The ELISA results were that of the whole protein extract (Figure S5F).

patient sera (1:4 diluted)	SPT (wheal/erythema, cm)	ImmunoCAP	ELISA
1	d72 (2*2/2*2) H (5*4/40*25)	--	-
2	d72 (2*2/10*10) H (6*6/30*30)	--	-
3	d72 (3*3/20*10) H (5*5/25*15)	--	+
4	d72 (4*4/20*20) H (5*4/20*20)	--	-
5	d72 (2*2/20*20) H (6*5/30*30)	--	+
6	d72 (2*2/20*20) H (3*2/30*30)	--	-
7	d72 (2*2/30*20) H (5*4/30*25)	--	+
8	d72 (5*5/15*15) H (4*4/20*10)	--	+
9	d72 (3*3/20*15) H (5*5/15*15)	--	-
10	d72 (2*2/10*10) H (3*3/10*10)	--	+
11	d72 (4*3/15*10) H (3*3/10*10)	--	+
12	d72 (3*3/7*5) H (4*4/15*15)	--	-
13	d72 (3*2/10*10) H (4*3/15*15)	--	+
14	d72 (3*2/10*10) H (5*4/20*20)	--	+
15	d72 (3*3/25*15) H (4*3/20*15)	--	+
16	d72 (4*3/20*20) H (4*3/30*20)	--	-
17	--	4+	+
18	--	3+	+

Table S3. Metadata of the patient sera pooled for 2D gel electrophoresis

Serum samples were obtained at The First Affiliated Hospital of Guangzhou Medical University (Guangzhou, China) from 25 patients (mean age, 19.9 years; range, 2–51 years) who were examined to be dust mite allergy.

Patient	Sample	Sex	Age	Diagnosis	d1 (<i>D. pteronyssinus</i>) *	
					Conc. (kU/l)	Level
85909	BJ1905	F	17yr	Allergic purpura	16.6	3
85963	BJ1964	M	51yr	Skin allergy	14.2	3
86332	BGM8857	F	3yr	Rhinitis	8.7	3
86432	BGM9094	F	2yr	Asthma	5.63	3
87631	BJ1085	M	33yr	Allergic dermatitis	17.4	3
87649	BJ1053	M	9yr	Allergic rhinitis	35.5	4
88216	BJ2203	M	6yr	Acute suppurative tonsillitis	6.59	3
89070	BJ3542	F	26yr	Rhinitis	13.8	3
89260	BGM9501	F	42yr	Allergic rhinitis	38.2	4
89580	BJ4754	F	12yr	Systemic lupus erythematosus	7.96	3
90444	BJ6422	F	16yr	Allergic purpura	5.7	3
90996	BJ7531	M	42yr	Acute urticaria	5.74	3
91503	BJ8361	F	21yr	Allergic dermatitis	4.33	3
91506	BJ8353	F	18yr	Allergic dermatitis	3.83	3
91510	BJ8356	M	7yr	Allergic dermatitis	25	4
91508	BJ8380	M	4yr	Allergic purpura	26.1	4
91523	BJ8443	M	39yr	Acute urticaria	14.3	3
91524	BJ8422	F	17yr	Allergic dermatitis	80.4	5
91525	BJ8426	M	7yr	Asthmatic bronchitis	85.3	5
91580	BGM102	F	32yr	Urticaria	11.1	3
91582	BGM150	M	36yr	Urticaria	4.5	3
91253	BJ7960	M	16yr	Allergic purpura	> 100	6
91554	BJ8525	F	13yr	Urticaria	> 100	6
91555	BJ8543	M	12yr	Urticaria	72.9	5
91557	BJ8462	F	17yr	Chronic urticaria	3.93	3

* These patient sera samples (obtained at The First Affiliated Hospital of Guangzhou Medical College, Guangzhou, China) were tested with ImmunoCAP kit (d1 for *D. pteronyssinus*) and their IgE reactivity were at least level 3 (IgE \geq 3.5 kU/l).

Figure S1. Gene synteny alignment of tandemly arrayed allergen genes.

Tandem gene duplications were observed in many allergen groups. All the distances between neighboring genes are below 5 kb.

Figure S3. Sequence alignment of Tyr p 3, 8, 20, 35 and 36

(A) Sequence alignment of Tyr p 3.0101 (gene locus: TP_012006.03) and the reported Tyr p 3 (GenBank accession: ABZ81991.1). (B) Sequence alignment of Tyr p 8.0101 (gene locus: TP_016261.02) and the reported Tyr p 8 (GenBank accession: AGG10560.1). (C) Sequence alignment of Tyr p 20.0101 (gene locus: TP_001138.03), Tyr p 20.0201 (gene locus: TP_001138.02) and the reported Tyr p 20 (GenBank accession: QOI58528.1). (D) Sequence alignment of Tyr p 35.0101 (gene locus: TP_014714.03) and the reported Tyr p 35 (GenBank accession: AOD75396.1). (E) Sequence alignment of Tyr p 36.0101 (gene locus: TP_007980.01) and the reported Tyr p 36 (GenBank accession: AOD75399.1). All the sequence alignments were performed by the online tool Clustal Omega.

Figure S4. SDS-PAGE analysis of purified recombinant proteins

The purified recombinant proteins were loaded and analyzed in SDS-PAGE. All the recombinant proteins were observed within the range of estimated molecular weights (in the brackets under protein IDs) \pm 5 KDa. The target bands of recombinant proteins were marked in arrows.

Figure S5. ELISA results for recombinant proteins and crude protein extract

The allergenicity of recombinant proteins and whole protein extract of *T. putrescentiae* was tested by ELISA using sera samples from 18 allergy patients (TP positive) and 13 healthy individuals (TP negative) as negative controls (Table S2). The y axis represents the absorbance values at 450 nm. The dotted lines indicate the cutoff value, mean+ 2*SD (standard deviation) of the negative controls. The allergenicity of recombinant proteins was as follows: **(A)** rTyr p 6.0101 (11.1%), **(B)** rTyr p 9.0101 (22.2%), **(C)** rTyr p 18.0101 (11.1%), **(D)** rTyr p 20.0101 (44.4%), **(E)** rTyr p 26.0101 (50.0%). Also, 11/18 (61.1%) of the patient serum samples showed positive responses to the crude protein extract **(F)**.

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CLUSTAL O(1.2.4) multiple sequence alignment

DF_001154.01  MISKILCLSLLV-----AAVVDQVDV 22
DP_010248.01  MMYKILCLSLLV-----AAVAADQVDV 22
Eur m_2.0101  -MYKILCLSLLV-----AAVAADQVDI 21
SS_011027.01  MLKYFLASVLLVAAYSLVISAYDQNFDFDQHSTSKSQPETITTNKPKDANKPKDFRDI AF 60
: :* . *** : : .

DF_001154.01  KDCANNEIKKVMVDGCHGSDPCIHRGKPFLEALFDANQNTKTAKIEIKASL-DGLEID 81
DP_010248.01  KDCANHEIKKVLVPGCHGSEPCIIHRGKPFQLEAVFEANQNSKTAKIEIKASI-DGLEVD 81
Eur m_2.0101  KDCANHEIKKVMVPGCKGSEPCVIHRGTAFQLEAVFDANQNSNAAKIEIKATI-DGVEID 80
SS_011027.01  TDCGNHELLHVRLTGCRGSI PCVLYRKS VVHLTAIFKSNQNTTAVVGLQATLPGGLELP 120
**.*.* : * : **.* **.* : * . . * * . . **.* . * : : * : : * . * :

DF_001154.01  VPGIDTNACHFVKCPLVKGQQYDIKYTWNVPKIAPKSENVVTVKLI GDNGLACAIATH 141
DP_010248.01  VPGIDPNACHYMKCPLVKGQQYDIKYTWNVPKIAPKSENVVTVKVMGDNGLACAIATH 141
Eur m_2.0101  VPGIDNNLCHFMCPLVKGQEYDIKYTWNVPR IAPKSENVVTVKLLGDNGLACAIATH 140
SS_011027.01  VPGVDTNACHHEHCPITCGSLVTFY PWWVPKFMPQF SNLTLKAYMEGEHGRMACGIITN 180
***.* * ** . ** . * . : * * * : * : * . : . . : * : * : * . * :

DF_001154.01  AKIRD 146
DP_010248.01  AKIRD 146
Eur m_2.0101  AKIRD 145
SS_011027.01  VSIR- 184
..**

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Figure S6. Multiple sequence alignment of N2 Cluster

Protein sequences of DF_001154.01, DP_010248.01, Eur m 2.0101 and SS_011027.01 were aligned by the online tool Clustal Omega. A fragment of unaligned sequences of SS_011027.01 was marked in the black square.

Figure S7. Expression levels of NPC2 family

Gene expression levels of NPC2 family of six astigmatic mites were quantified as TPM using transcriptome data of adult mites. The SRA accessions were labeled in the axis. TP1 and TP3 of SRR13837414 transcriptome data were used for genes of *T. putrescentiae* (labeled 1 and 3, respectively). The most highly expressed genes were in Cluster N1, N2 and N3, except one *S. scabiei* gene in Cluster C1, and one *D. farinae* gene and one *T. putrescentiae* gene in Cluster C3.

Figure S8. Phylogenetic analysis and expression levels of GSTs

(A) Phylogenetic analysis of GSTs of six astigmatic mites. The GST genes were divided into six clusters, including EF1G that contains a eukaryotic elongation factor 1 gamma (eEF1 γ) conserved domain on C terminal and prostaglandin E synthase 2 (PTGES2) that has GST activity. The GST allergens including group 8 of astigmatic mites (highlighted in red) were collected from the WHO/IUIS nomenclature database. Tandemly arrayed genes and proximally arrayed genes (separated by no more than 10 genes) were connected by curved solid lines and dotted lines, respectively. The black triangle marked the GST gene identified in Table 1. (B) Gene expression levels of GSTs of *T. putrescentiae* were quantified as TPM using two transcriptome data of adult mites (TP1 and TP3 of SRR13837414).

Figure S9. ELISA result for the recombinant FK506-binding protein (TP_004518.01)
 The allergenicity of the recombinant FK506-binding protein (TP_004518.01) of *T. putrescentiae* was tested by ELISA using sera samples from 18 allergy patients (TP positive) and 13 healthy individuals (TP negative) as negative controls (Table S2). The y axis represents the absorbance values at 450 nm. The dotted lines indicate the cutoff value, mean+ 2*SD (standard deviation) of the negative controls. The allergenicity 22.2% (4/18).

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